

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BUSHELL****FIRST NAME: NADINE****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: SIX (6)****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US*The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:*The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

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QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. “Paraphrases are the ideas and information that an author has produced on a topic but written in your own words” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 36). Which one of the following is a principle of good paraphrasing?
- The writing style you use to express the author’s ideas must be different from the style the author used.¹**
 - The language you use can resemble the words of the author once you rearrange the sentence structure.
 - Once you rearrange the sentence structure and use a different writing style and use your own words, you are not required to cite the work the information came from.
 - The paraphrase you use must not look very different than how the author originally wrote it.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401DCoursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. (Bangui Euclid University, 2021), 36.

2. All of the following are signs of the reliability of research sources except one.
- The book or article is not peered reviewed.**²
 - The source is only available online, but it is sponsored by a reputable organization.
 - The source is a book, and it has been well reviewed.
 - The source has been frequently cited by others.
3. What are the three elements at the core of your argument?
- Your claim, your reasons for accepting it, and the evidence on which those reasons are based.**³
 - Your claim, your reasons for accepting it, and the limitations of the argument.
 - Your claim, the limitations of the argument, and the relevance of the claim.
 - Your claim, the limitations of the argument, and the warrant.
4. Which one of the following figure/table designs is suitable for depicting specific values?
- One.**⁴

² Kate L Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* Ninth edition (Chicago; London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 42.

³ Ibid., 56-64.

⁴ Ibid., 86-87.

Family type	Percentage of total families				
	1970	1980	1990	2000	2010
2 parents	85	77	73	68	64
Mother	11	18	22	23	27
Father	1	2	3	4	4
No adult	3	4	3	4	4

Changes in family Structure, 1970 - 2010

Two

Changes in family Structure, 1970 – 2010

Three

Changes in family Structure, 1970 – 2010

- Four
 - None of the above
5. Which of the following is not the purpose of the literature review in a dissertation?
- Provides a brief summary of and rationale for how data were analysed.**⁵
 - Justifies how the study addresses a gap or problem in the literature.
 - reviews primary sources that are mostly recent empirical studies from scholarly journals and publications, as well as secondary sources.
 - synthesizes findings across studies and compares and contrasts different research outcomes, perspectives, or methods.

⁵ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2018), 77-78.

6. Which of the following defines Ethnography?

- A form of qualitative research focused on discovering and describing the culture of a group from the perspectives of the members themselves. Reports of data gathered through multiple methods, typically in-depth interviews and participant observation.⁶**
- An in-depth exploration from multiple perspectives of the richness and complexity of a bounded social phenomenon (or multiple phenomena), be this a social unit or system such as a program, event, institution, organization, or community. The purpose is to generate understanding and deep insights to inform professional practice, policy development, and community or social action.
- A systematic, collaborative, and democratic orientation toward inquiry that seeks effective solutions to complex problems that people confront in their communities and organizations (McNiff, 2018; Mertler, 2017; Stringer, 2014). The research process is iterative, cyclical, and participative in nature and is intended to foster deeper understanding of a given situation informing future action, starting with conceptualizing and particularizing the problem and moving through several interventions and evaluations. The research studies have direct relevance to improving practice and advocating for change. This type of research is especially valuable to those involved in professional, organizational, educational, and community research, with a focus on engaging stakeholders in collaborative relationships and working on developing localized solutions.
- Is most appropriately employed in studies where little is known about a phenomenon of interest. Its purpose is to inductively generate theory that is grounded in, or emerges from, the data. The goal is to move beyond description and to have the researcher generate or discover a theory of a process, an action, or an interaction grounded in the views of the research participants.

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, 164.

7. Which of the following gives the best description of synthesis?
- The act of making connections between those parts identified in the analysis.**⁷
 - Where information is pulled together and listed to highlight important key points.
 - Addresses distinct sets of information. Each piece of information or source remains distinct and separate.
 - Presents a summary of each source or study one after the next.
8. All but one of these are trustworthiness criteria.
- Limitations – those characteristics of design or methodology that impacted or influenced the interpretation of the findings from the research.*⁸
 - Confirmability – concerned with establishing the researcher’s findings and interpretations are clearly derived from the data, requiring the researcher to demonstrate how conclusions have been reached.
 - Dependability – the researcher must ensure that the research process is clearly documented, logical, and traceable. This refers to the stability and consistency of data over time.
 - Credibility – whether the participants’ perceptions match up with the researcher’s portrayal of them.
9. Which one of the following statements best explains your research purpose?

⁷ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, 385.

⁸ Ibid., 473-476.

The major objective or intent of the study and enables readers to understand the research problem.⁹

- Serves a foundational role in that it communicates what is the formal reason for engaging in the dissertation in the first place.
- Illustrates the reasons why your study should be conducted.
- Includes some background and context for the issue that is in need of exploration and also provides a rationale for the importance of the topic.

10. Which type of coding is not applicable to the three stages of analysis central to grounded theory?

Data coding - the process of deriving codes from the observed data.¹⁰

- Open coding – procedures for identifying and naming the data and developing categories of information.
- Selective coding – looking for the story line of the theory by reflecting on the data and the findings that were produced in previous coding phases.
- Axial coding – interconnecting the categories and looking for relationships among them.

⁹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, 242.

¹⁰ Ibid., 273.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401DCoursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition. Chicago; London: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.